

Trajectory Optimization with Reinforcement Learning-driven Control of Multi-Arm Robots in On-Orbit Servicing Operations

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Intelligent motion planning and control systems are crucial in managing the inherently unpredictable and non-deterministic conditions of space. Trajectory optimization (TO) has been a key method in space robotics for precision control and guidance. However, the effectiveness of TO is limited by its reliance on accurate robotic and environmental models. Reinforcement Learning (RL) has emerged as a promising alternative, enhancing robustness and adaptability in control systems. Unlike TO, RL does not depend on predefined models but learns effective control policies through simulated interactions. This model-free approach has shown potential in handling complex control tasks and adapting to environmental uncertainties and perturbations. This paper proposes an integrated TO and RL approach for enhanced path planning and control of a four-arm robot designed for on-orbit servicing tasks. By combining the predictive power of TO with the adaptive capabilities of RL, this approach aims to optimize the robot's operational effectiveness. The integration seeks to leverage the detailed pre-planned motion profiles provided by TO, while incorporating the flexibility and resilience of RL-based control strategies to accommodate real-time operational dynamics and uncertainties. The results presented demonstrate how this hybrid approach can significantly improve the robot's trajectory tracking performance and operational adaptability.

1 Introduction

In-space assembly (ISA) will require the use of robots as an alternative to astronauts performing extravehicular activities. Stationary [1], free-flyers [2] [3], and crawling robots [4] can be used in this kind of tasks. Crawling robots are considered for ISA tasks when the robot manipulators are attached to a base that can be relocated by using the manipulators motion. This last approach is the one proposed in this paper. A four-arm crawling robot is considered that operates near the target spacecraft, enabling its arm's end-effectors to reach the spacecraft's surface. Connections to the target spacecraft can be established by

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Figure 1: Multi-arm robot in Isaac Sim.

the arms through specific footholds (docking devices) or by gripping onto structural elements.

For the execution of such tasks, intelligent motion planning and control systems are of great interest due to their high adaptability to uncertain and non-deterministic workspaces. Trajectory optimization (TO) has been a recent trend in the space robotics community for guidance and control, with promising results in on-orbit manipulation applications [5, 6]. Similar works focus on control of multilegged robots, where the optimization task is represented as a set of constraints and decision variables [7, 8]. Additional constraints for the guidance of the on-orbit four-arm robot considered in this work are explored in [9].

Despite their widespread use, TO methods are not without limitations. They need an accurate model of the kinematics and dynamics of the robot, as well as a precise representation of the environment where it operates. These models influence not only the planning stage, but also the subsequent control, due to the assumptions made during the modelling stage.

To tackle some of the shortcomings of TO methods, Reinforcement Learning (RL) has risen as a new paradigm for robust and adaptive motion control.

One of the principal advantages of RL is that it doesn't rely on explicit models. Instead, a control policy is learned through interactions of agents within their environment, commonly in simulation. This approach has shown impressive results in complex control problems such as legged locomotion [10, 11] and navigation [12], also within complex, cluttered environments [13], and for learning design-conditioned policies for subsequent design optimization [14].

This success in terrestrial applications is making RL a more appealing approach also for control of space systems. One of the more common uses of RL in space is in the field of spacecraft guidance, navigation, and control (GNC) [15]. Nevertheless, RL is not yet a common approach in on-orbit servicing operations. However, some works showcase its potential use to cope with the complexities of on-orbit scenarios [16].

Even with all its benefits, RL has its own set of drawbacks. These algorithms do not exploit the knowledge of the operational environment to the same extent as model-based approaches. Furthermore, it might be challenging to learn contact-intensive tasks where valid footholds are constrained, as these scenarios may not occur frequently enough in simulation. In order to mitigate these flaws, a hybrid TO-RL approach can be highly beneficial in order to exploit the advantages of both worlds [17]. This is the case for on-orbit applications like ISA, where we might have partial knowledge of the operation space that allows us to have a pre-planned motion, but where we could also need some adaptability and robustness to mismatch in our modelling of the system and task.

This paper proposes a trajectory optimization and model-free reinforcement learning approach for the path planning and control of the four-arm robot in an on-orbit servicing scenario. The proposed RL-based motion control is compared with model-based approaches. As the results show, the presented approach allows to improve the tracking performance taking advantage of the adaptive capabilities of RL agents.

2 Methodology

2.1 Trajectory Optimization

In this paper, the path planning and control of the four-arm robot shown in Figure 1 is proposed. The joint coordinates of each arm are represented as $\mathbf{q}_i \in \mathcal{R}^n$ where $i = 1 \dots 4$, and $n = 6$ are the degrees of freedom of each arm. The robot arms are in close proximity to the target spacecraft surface, enabling its arm end-effectors to reach the surface of the target spacecraft. This paper assumes that the target spacecraft has a much greater mass than the multi-arm robot.

The target's motion does not change significantly due to the interaction with the robot's end-effectors. Contrarily, reaction forces produced by the contact dynamics can produce significant changes in both the position and orientation of the robot base. The four-arm robot path-planning is generated by using a TO approach based on the formulation of an Optimal Control Problem (OCP).

Considering \mathbf{t}_b the linear robot body Center of Mass (CoM) and ϕ_b its orientation, the information required by the trajectory optimization algorithm is the initial robot body location $[\mathbf{t}_b^T(t=0) = \mathbf{t}_{b0}^T, \phi_b^T(t=0) = \phi_{b0}^T]^T$, the final or desired robot body location $[\mathbf{t}_b^T(t=T) = \mathbf{t}_{bd}^T, \phi_b^T(t=T) = \phi_{bd}^T]^T$, the number of graspings for each arm, N_i , and the total duration of the maneuver, T . The OCP automatically generates, the robot body trajectory, $[\mathbf{t}_b^T(t), \phi_b^T(t)]^T$, the manipulators end effector trajectories, $\mathbf{p}_i(t)$, the interaction forces of each arm end-effector with respect the contact surface, $\mathbf{f}_i(t)$, and the required gait for each arm during the trajectory. The formulation of the OCP also includes a set of constraints which can be seen in our previous studies [6, 9].

In addition, the specific kinematics and dynamics of the four-arm robot should be included as constraints to guarantee both the manipulators' range of motion and realistic motion path planning given the robot's dynamics. On the one hand, to guarantee the robot arms motion are within the corresponding workspace, the kinematic constraints are defined as a prism centred at each arm nominal position. This prism defines the robot workspace and limits the manipulators range of motion. On the other hand, the robot arms dynamics constraint is defined by the following equation:

$$\mathbf{M}_i^* \ddot{\mathbf{q}}_i + \mathbf{C}_i^* = \boldsymbol{\tau}_i + \boldsymbol{\tau}_{envi} \quad (1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\tau}_{envi} \in \mathcal{R}^n$ are the environmental perturbation torques acting on arm i , $\mathbf{M}_i^* \in \mathcal{R}^{n \times n}$ is the arm i generalised inertia matrix, and $\mathbf{C}_i^* \in \mathcal{R}^n$ is the corresponding generalised Coriolis and centrifugal vector. Matrices \mathbf{M}_i^* and \mathbf{C}_i^* can be defined by using the following equations:

$$\mathbf{M}_i^* = \mathbf{M}_{ii} - \mathbf{M}_{bi}^T \mathbf{M}_{bb}^{-1} \mathbf{M}_{bi} \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_i^* = \mathbf{c}_{mi} - \mathbf{M}_{bi}^T \mathbf{M}_{bb}^{-1} \mathbf{c}_b \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{M}_{ii} \in \mathcal{R}^{n \times n}$ is the inertia matrix of the arm i , $\mathbf{M}_{bi} \in \mathcal{R}^{6 \times n}$ is the coupled inertia matrix between the robot base and the arm i , $\mathbf{M}_{bb} \in \mathcal{R}^{6 \times 6}$ is the inertia matrix of the robot base, and \mathbf{c}_b , and \mathbf{c}_{mi} , are a velocity/displacement-dependent, non-linear terms for the robot base and arm i , respectively.

Finally, the function to be optimized by the OCP is the following:

$$\int_0^T \sum_1^{\zeta} [\sigma_{i1}(f_i^x(t))^2 + \sigma_{i2}(f_i^y(t))^2 + \sigma_{i3}(f_i^z(t))^2] + \sigma_{i4}(\dot{t}_b^x(t))^2 + \sigma_{i5}(\dot{t}_b^y(t))^2 + \sigma_{i6}(\dot{t}_b^z(t))^2 dt \quad (4)$$

where $f_i^x(t)$, $f_i^y(t)$, $f_i^z(t)$ are the robot manipulators end-effector contact forces in x , y , and z , $\dot{t}_b^x(t)$, $\dot{t}_b^y(t)$, $\dot{t}_b^z(t)$ are the robot base velocities in each direction, and σ_i are weights for each constraint term. These functions are included in the cost function in order to reduce the required contact forces and to obtain smooth trajectories in the robot body.

From this information an RL-based control approach is proposed for tracking the manipulators end-effector trajectories $\mathbf{p}_i(t)$.

2.2 RL-driven Motion Control

In order to use an RL-based approach to control the robot's arms and follow the planned trajectory, we need to model the problem of end-effector position tracking as a Markov Decision Process (MDP) [18].

An MDP is defined by a state space \mathcal{S} , action space \mathcal{A} , a probability density function defining the transition probabilities between states $\mathcal{P}(s_{t+1}|s_t, a_t)$, and a reward function describing the task to be achieved $\mathcal{R}(s_t, a_t, s_{t+1}) : \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{S} \mapsto \mathbb{R}$. At each timestep, the agent observes the environment and gets a state $s_t \in \mathcal{S}$. Then, it takes an action $a_t \in \mathcal{A}$ based on its policy $\pi_\theta(a_t|s_t)$. After this interaction, the agent receives a reward signal r_t . The final goal of RL is adjusting the parameters θ of the policy π_θ to obtain an optimal policy which maximizes the cumulative discounted rewards $\mathbb{E}[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t r_t]$, with γ being the discount factor. This is achieved through an iterative process consisting of sequential interactions with the environment, in a "trial and error" fashion.

In our trajectory tracking scenario, we define the MDP as follows. The state space \mathcal{S} comprises the current base position \mathbf{t}_b and orientation ϕ_b in quaternion form, the joint positions and velocities, the desired Cartesian positions of each arm end-effector in base frame, the current positions of the end-effectors, and finally the actions taken by the policy in the previous step.

We define the action space \mathcal{A} as the desired joint positions for each leg at that time step. This desired positions are then forwarded to a PD controller running at a higher frequency. This is the typical action space selected for robotic joint control, because the agent can learn to adjust this joint position commands in a

way that its accuracy in following the desired position reference is much higher while still maintaining its model-free property, as it has been shown in previous works [10–12, 19].

For the reward function, we use three groups of rewards: Task rewards R_{task} which represent the main objective of our agent, regularization rewards R_{reg} that aim to reduce abrupt motions, and penalty rewards R_{pen} that make the agent avoid certain undesired states. The final reward is $R = R_{task} + R_{reg} + R_{pen}$. Each of the reward terms has a weighting factor w , which adjusts the importance of each factor in the total reward and also serves as a normalization value.

1) *Task reward*: We provide a dense logarithmic function to perform end-effector pose tracking. We use the logarithmic function to achieve higher gradients when the error is lower, thus favouring the learning in the later stages of training. The terms for position and orientation tracking are defined as:

$$R_{task} = w_{pos} \cdot -\ln(\|\mathbf{p}_i^* - \mathbf{p}_i\|^2 + \epsilon) + w_{orient} \cdot -\ln(\|\psi\| + \epsilon) \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{p}_i^* and \mathbf{p}_i are the desired and measured end-effector positions for arm i , and ψ is the axis angle representation of the rotation error between the desired orientation and the current orientation, computed as the multiplication of the quaternion representing the desired orientation, and the conjugate of the quaternion of the current orientation. Lastly, $0 < \epsilon \ll 1$ is a small number ensuring that the function is well-defined. In our case, we set $\epsilon = 10^{-5}$, and $w_{pos} = w_{orient} = 15.0$.

2) *Regularization reward*: These terms aim to reduce jerky moves, promoting smooth motions of the legs and the base. We penalize high values in terms of joint power, joint accelerations, body acceleration, and difference in consecutive actions. This term is defined as:

$$R_{reg} = w_{pow} \cdot \sum_i (\dot{\mathbf{q}}_i^T \boldsymbol{\tau}_i)^2 + w_{acc} \cdot \sum_i \ddot{\mathbf{q}}_i^2 + w_{body} \cdot (\|\ddot{\mathbf{t}}_b\| + \|\ddot{\phi}_b\|) + w_{act} \cdot \sum_i (\mathbf{a}_{i,t} - \mathbf{a}_{i,t-1})^2 \quad (6)$$

where $\dot{\mathbf{q}}_i$, $\ddot{\mathbf{q}}_i$ and $\boldsymbol{\tau}_i$ are the joint velocities, accelerations, and torques, respectively. $\ddot{\mathbf{t}}_b$ and $\ddot{\phi}_b$ are the body linear and angular accelerations, and $\mathbf{a}_t, \mathbf{a}_{t-1}$ are the actions taken by the policy at the current and previous timesteps. Here, we set $w_{pow} = -5 \times 10^{-3}$, $w_{acc} = -5 \times 10^{-6}$, $w_{body} = -1 \times 10^{-3}$, and $w_{act} = -1 \times 10^{-2}$.

3) *Penalty reward*: We heavily penalize undesired states to ensure that our agent avoids them. More specifically, we penalize contacts of the arms between them or with themselves, and strongly punish contacts with the robot body. These penalties are defined

as follows:

$$R_{pen} = w_c \cdot n_c + w_{bc} \cdot b_c \tag{7}$$

where n_c is the number of contacts between the arms, and $b_c \in \{0, 1\}$, with $b_c = 1$ denotes termination due to a body collision. We set $w_c = -1$ and $w_{bc} = -10$.

Finally, the policy $\pi_\theta(a_t|s_t)$ is modeled as a Multi-Layer Perceptron as in [20], with similar hyperparameters, and PPO is selected as the learning algorithm [21].

3 Results

3.1 Training details

The policies are trained using the Orbit robot learning framework [22] and *Isaac Sim* simulator [23]. The four-arm multipod robot is spawned in the simulator in the starting position shown in Figure 1. To introduce the nuances of on-orbit operations, we remove gravity from the simulation so that the policy learns to manage the internal reaction forces generated from the robot’s own motion.

Observation and action spaces are described in Section 2.2, as well as the reward function. The position commands for each end-effector are uniformly sampled inside a sphere of radius $0.2m$ around the starting position of each end-effector, and change every $6s$. We restrict the target positions to be inside the sphere to ensure that are reachable for the arm. The episode is terminated every $12s$ or when a collision of the body is detected. At each reset, the initial joint positions are randomized within a $\pm 25\%$ of the default value to learn to cope with inaccuracies in the starting position. The policy and the PD controller run at $50Hz$ and $200Hz$ respectively, as in [17]. We train the policy with 8192 parallel environments and a batch size of 24×8192 , which takes $10h$ for 20000 epochs on an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090Ti.

3.2 Simulation Experiments

We evaluate the performance of our agent by testing the tracking performance when the target position is updated at fixed time intervals. To do so, we use an OCP-based approach to define two reference trajectories that are common in on-orbit servicing applications: A linear trajectory that could be done to reach a certain operation point, and a semi-circular trajectory representing a typical motion of an arm displacement to navigate to a new location. In both experiments, the orientation command is fixed to the orientation where the end-effector faces the XY plane, which would allow it to step on any docking device or grasp a suitable structural device.

Figure 2: Linear and Arc test trajectories. Blue shows planned trajectory and red illustrates the real trajectory followed by the arm.

We define a linear trajectory along the XZ plane of $0.28m$ length to be carried out in $10s$. Every $0.05s$ the next point in the trajectory is fed to the policy as the target position, and the policy needs to output the sequence of actions that leads to minimize the error between the current and desired positions.

For the second experiment, we define a slightly more complex trajectory consisting of a semi-circular trajectory similar to one that the robot would do when locomoting through a surface. The planned arc has radius $0.2m$, so the total displacement carried out by the end-effector is of $0.2\pi m$ in the XZ plane. The maximum time to complete the trajectory in this experiment is $15s$, with the same target update rate that in the linear trajectory.

Figure 2 exemplifies the trajectories used at test time, as well as the tracking performance of the right-front (RF) arm. These trajectories are simplified cases

Figure 3: Trajectory Tracking Performance. Upper row: Linear trajectory tracking. Bottom row: Arc tracking performance. Planned trajectories are drawn in magenta, dark green and cyan, and real trajectories in red, light green and blue, for the X, Y and Z axis respectively.

of common tasks that will be carried out by robots in ISA operations, such as moving an arm to operate on some part of the spacecraft (linear trajectory) or locomoting across the spacecraft’s surface to reach a certain target position (arc trajectory).

Figure 3 shows the results of using our policy to follow the desired trajectories. The plots show the evolution of the coordinates in each axis separately, for both planned and real trajectories, for each of the arms.

4 Discussion, Conclusions, and Future Work

This section aims to analyze the results shown in Section 3, in order to validate our RL-based approach and the obtained control policy. To do so, we will frame this analysis both qualitatively and quantitatively.

For a qualitative analysis, the tracking performance for both linear and semi-circular trajectories is shown in Figure 3. It can be seen how the end-effector of each arm follows the planned trajectory with considerable accuracy in each of the Cartesian directions.

Quantitatively, we compute the mean tracking error for each arm’s end-effector when tracking the trajectories explained in Section 3.2. These metrics are shown in Table 1. It can be seen how the policy manages to guide every arm accurately, with errors of around $7 \times 10^{-3} m$.

Comparing our results with previous model-based

Arm ID	Linear	Arc
LF	7.4×10^{-3}	8.2×10^{-3}
LH	7.8×10^{-3}	7.3×10^{-3}
RF	5.0×10^{-3}	6.1×10^{-3}
RH	5.0×10^{-3}	8.9×10^{-3}

Table 1: Mean tracking error for each arm (in meters)

works about task-space control of multi-arm robots in on-orbit applications [24], our model-free RL policy outperforms the tracking performance of model-based approaches. This comparison is summarized in Table 2.

In conclusion, we presented a hybrid TO-RL approach for planning and control of a multi-arm robot for on-orbit servicing applications. We evaluated the trained policy for both position and trajectory tracking, showing that we can outperform model-based methods by using model-free RL, gaining the robustness to disturbances of this techniques, while also leveraging the knowledge about the task that can be exploited by TO algorithms.

Future work should seek to test the policy in more complex trajectories which are more representative of on-orbit servicing operations. In addition, the performance while interacting with docking devices or structural grasping points should as well be studied. Lastly, other RL techniques which provide more the-

Controller	Mean error (m)
PD Controller	2.7×10^{-2}
Velocity-based	2.3×10^{-2}
Acceleration-based	1.2×10^{-2}
Force-based controller	1.4×10^{-2}
Optimal control approach	9.3×10^{-3}
RL-based (ours)	6.9×10^{-3}

Table 2: Mean Control Errors during Tracking

oretical guarantees of satisfying a certain set of constraints are also of great interest for the ISA field, and will be explored in subsequent work.

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